

USING COLLABORATIVE STRATEGIC READING TO IMPROVE STUDENT'S READING SKILL AT VIII-A GRADE STUDENTS OF SMP NEGERI 3 BAYONGBONG

Tedi Kurniawan

Teacher at SMP Negeri 3 Bayongbong Kabupaten Garut

kokoberuang@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study entitled, "Using Collaborative Strategic Reading to Improve Learner's Reading Skill" is aimed to investigate the effect of Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) as one of comprehension strategy instruction proposed by Klingner et. al (1998) on students' reading comprehension. The study applied four CSR' reading strategies: preview, click & clunk, get the gist, and wrap up in the classroom. The method of the research is Classroom Action Research in which the participants were eighth graders at SMP Negeri 3 Bayongbong.

Keywords: Reading, Collaborative Strategic Reading, Classroom Action Research

INTRODUCTION

Reading is the most important source of language learning.¹ In the EFL context, literature suggested that the second best way to learn English, other than living among its speakers, is to read extensively in English.² However, about 8 million adolescents struggle with literacy in middle and high school, according to an expert panel of reading researchers. "Very few of these older struggling readers need help to read the words on a page; their most common problem is that they are not able to comprehend what they read . . . Obviously, the challenge is not a small one"³ Despite the importance of reading, there are many EFL students who have difficulties in understanding English texts. There are many factors that may cause them difficult to comprehend the text. The main factors may be the lack of vocabularies and their background knowledge of the topics. There are several research have been conducted to find the best methods to help students understand English text. Among various reading methods, Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) proposed by Klingner and Vaughn⁴ is a method designed to improve learners' strategic reading abilities through small group discussion. CSR uses a mix of whole class instruction and small cooperative learning groups, so that a teacher can work with an entire class at the same time Students learn in four strategies as a part of CSR's plan including 'preview', 'click & clunk', 'get the gist', and 'wrap up'. The 'preview' strategy is only used before students read the text while 'wrap up' is only used after students reading the entire text. The other two strategies, 'click & clunk' and 'get the gist' are applied during the reading process.

One of the purposes of CSR is to fulfill the students' learning needs in a class population which have diverse ability, especially for the students with learning disabilities. There are several previous CSR researches for example, a research conducted by Klingner and Vaughn in 1996 with 26 Latino middle school students with learning disabilities. The result of the study showed that students gain their

comprehension even when they are not provided with teacher's instruction in reading class. CSR also have been implemented for English as Foreign Language (EFL) students.⁵ A research on CSR in Taiwanese fifth-grade classroom has been conducted by Lee, and the results showed that CSR helped her students improve their reading comprehension more than traditional instruction⁶.

METHODS

The type of research used is Classroom Action Research (CAR). The writer use this research method because want to improve student's reading skills, in line with Creswell's goal of action research. That is to improve educational practice, study learning problems or problems in schools or educational environments.⁷ The purpose of this research is to bridge the gap between learning theory and practice, which refers to Kunandar's opinion that the purpose of CAR is to improve the learning process in the classroom.⁸ CAR is research that describes the cause and effect of treatment, as well as describes what happens when the treatment is given, and describes the entire process from the beginning of giving treatment to the impact of the treatment given to the subject of the action.⁹ In addition, CAR is also a form of reflective research conducted by teachers whose results can be used as a tool for curriculum development, school development, teaching skill development, and so on.

The location of the research was at SMP Negeri 3 Bayongbong, Kabupaten Garut. From August 6th, 2021 to August 20th, 2021, only VIII-A students at SMP Negeri 3 Bayongbong with total of thirty two students, consisting of seventeen female and fifteen male.

RESULTS

The research was conducted in early August 2021 to mid-August 2021 consisting of two cycles. Each cycle is carried out three times face to face (meeting). The findings of each cycle can be described as follows:

Results of activities in each cycle (pre-cycle, cycles I and II)

No.	Observed Variables	Numbers and Percentages		
		Pre-cycle	Cycle I	Cycle II
1.	Average Scores	57.66	67.34	76.09
2.	Total students who were successful in the CSR Method	18 out of 32 students	22 out of 32 students	26 out of 32 students
3.	Total students who were not successful in the CSR Method	14 out of 32 students	10 out of 32 students	6 out of 32 students
4.	Percentage of students who were successful in the CSR Method	56.25%	68.75%	81.25%
5.	Percentage of students who were not successful in the CSR Method	43.75%	31.25%	18.75%

Chart of the percentage students who have succeeded CSR Method

Based on the analysis results of student activities with the application of the CSR method, it can be seen that the results achieved by students have increased, this indicates that the learning delivery through the CSR method can improve students' reading skills.

Based on the results of the study, there was a change in the average value from cycle I to cycle II. This is because in cycle I there were students who did not really understand the CSR method and there were also those who did not pay attention to the teacher's explanation when the teacher gave examples of how learning activities use the CSR method.

Based on the table above, students have reached the level of developmental achievement, so it can be concluded that the CSR method can improve the reading ability of VIII-A students at SMP Negeri 3 Bayongbong, Garut.

CONCLUSION

The application of Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) received positive responses from the students. It can be seen from the learning process that most student believed that they could understand an English text better and faster after experiencing CSR as comprehension strategy instruction. Based on the results from cycle I and cycle II, it can be seen from the improvement in students' reading skills obtained from each cycle, during the pre-cycle or before the action was carried out the average students score was 57.66 with the number of students who were successful in the CSR Method namely 18 out of 32 students (56.25%), and after the action was taken in cycle I the average students score was 67.34 with the number of students who successful 22 out of 32 students (68.75%) and increased in cycle II with the average score of 76.09 with the number of students who successful 26 students out of 6 total (81.25%).

The students also thought that the implementation of CSR were fun and feel motivated because they studied the material with group which make the students

with lack English reading skill were helped by the other member of group. It was different with conventional learning processes which tend to make student learn individually.

However, in implementing CSR, there were at least, three disadvantages. It can be applied with large number of students, with several reading texts, and with good classroom management because the classroom can be very noisy and tended to be rather difficult to be controlled.

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⁸ Winarto, *Penelitian Tindakan Kelas Kompetensi Pedagogik Kelompok J* (Direktorat Jenderal Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2016) 2

⁹ Suharsimi Arikunto, Supardi, and Suhardjono, *Penelitian Tindakan Kelas: Edisi Revisi*, ed. Suryani (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2021).4